

Multi Fidelity Moving Particles Algorithm Considering Aleatory and Epistemic Uncertainty*

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Abstract. Calculating the probability of failure in structural reliability analysis often faces high computational costs. The costs increase further if imprecise probabilities are present, since an optimization problem must be solved for each evaluation of the model. In this paper, a multi fidelity algorithm based on the moving particles method is proposed to reduce the number of cost intensive model evaluations needed. It uses either additive or multiplicative information fusion to combine the different model fidelity outputs. Furthermore, probability boxes are used to represent the imprecise probabilities. The resulting multi fidelity estimator is tested on two examples. It is shown that a reduction of relative error and variance is achieved, but depends on the posed problem. This results in fewer evaluations of the high fidelity model if the same relative error is used as a termination threshold.

Keywords: reliability estimation, information fusion, multi fidelity, moving particles algorithm, imprecise probabilities, probability boxes

1 Introduction

In structural reliability analysis the probability of failure p_f is evaluated with respect to a quantity of interest (e.g. displacement or stress). For given random input parameters x of dimension d with joint probability density function $p(x)$ and input domain $\mathcal{D} \in \mathbb{R}^d$, the failure probability is calculated as

$$p_f = \int_{\mathcal{F}_F} p(x) dx \quad (1)$$

with failure domain $\mathcal{F}_F = \{x \in \mathcal{D} | g(x) < 0\}$. The limit state function (LSF) $g(x)$ becomes negative if the model response for the input parameters is greater than a given threshold for the quantity of interest. Usually a Monte Carlo Simulation (MCS) is carried out, since the integral over \mathcal{F}_F is not analytically tractable or the LSF defining the bounds of the failure domain is highly nonlinear. MCS is independent of the dimension of the input domain, but converges rather slowly,

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especially if p_f is small. [17]

Furthermore, the evaluation of the LSF can be computationally intensive. Therefore, advanced sampling techniques, also known as variance reduction techniques, which evaluate less samples for the same estimator accuracy, have been introduced. For importance sampling, samples are drawn from a better suited distribution to cover the failure domain and those samples are re-weighted afterwards such that the bias from sampling a different distribution vanishes. [18]

Additionally, there are so called importance splitting techniques which calculate the probability of failure by using intermediate failure domains which create conditional distributions. From these, samples are drawn via Markov Chain Monte Carlo simulation (MCMC). To compute p_f , all conditional probabilities are multiplied. This leads to a computational advantage since the conditional probabilities are large compared to p_f and thus it is possible to estimate them with a low coefficient of variation from rather few samples. Importance splitting methods comprise subset simulation with a fixed intermediate failure threshold (e.g. $p_0 = 0.1$) [3] and the moving particle algorithm with a maximum number of intermediate failure domains [11].

Another way to improve the estimator is by combining multiple models of either varying levels with discretization parameter h , also known as multi level estimators, introduced by [9] and [12], or of different fidelities, where no restrictions on the model types are made [20]. In the latter approach surrogate models can be implemented easily, however the correlation of the models has to be high in order to achieve an efficient estimator. [22] introduced a multi level version of the moving particles method leading to a considerable reduction of computational cost.

The majority of the scientific literature considers aleatory uncertainties, but there exist uncertainties caused by not knowing the underlying system and its parameters completely, referred to as epistemic uncertainties. The latter can be reduced with more effort, e.g. more measurements, and therefore higher costs. [6]

Another term for the combination of aleatory and epistemic uncertainties is imprecise probability. These imprecise probabilities can be captured using intervals [29], fuzzy variables [27], probability boxes (p-boxes) [8] or combinations thereof. Importance sampling has also been extended to capture intervals [28]. [2] applied importance splitting for discretized p-boxes. [24] presented a combination of surrogate models and p-boxes to compute the probability of failure. Despite these advances, a multi fidelity approach including imprecise probabilities does not exist. The moving particles algorithm is suitable in particular since it is easily adaptable for a multi fidelity setting and has a sound mathematical foundation rooted in Poisson process theory.

The paper is structured as follows: at first, the applied methods are explained in detail in Section 2. This includes the moving particles algorithm, multi fidelity estimators and p-boxes. Second, in Section 3 the multi fidelity moving particles estimator (MFMP) is introduced and its adaption to p-boxes is described. Third, the estimator is applied to a simple academic example and a single de-

gree of freedom (SDOF) oscillator in Section 4. Lastly, conclusions are drawn and future research is pointed out in Section 5.

2 Methods

Starting with the moving particles algorithm the fundamental concepts and methods are introduced. Herein, additive and multiplicative multi fidelity estimators are presented, afterwards the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm for a multivariate Poisson distribution is explained and lastly, imprecise probabilities in the form of p-boxes are described.

2.1 Moving Particles Algorithm

The moving particles algorithm gives an estimate of the probability of failure p_f . The algorithm starts with an initial MCS in the input domain $\mathcal{D} \in \mathbb{R}^d$ with a prior joint distribution. d is the number of input dimensions. Each sample $x_i \in \mathcal{D}, i = 1, \dots, N$ – called particle in this section – and its LSF evaluation $g(x_i)$ are sorted such that the one with the highest value g_{\max} (farthest away from the failure domain \mathcal{F}_F) is taken as the first one to move. Now the aim is to reduce the value of the LSF, such that $g(x_{i,\text{new}}) < g(x_i)$. All other particles currently fulfill this criterion and are part of a conditional distribution resulting from the prior distribution with condition $g(x_i) < g_{\max}$, which needs to be sampled from. This is done by performing MCMC with one of the particles in the remaining set being the starting point of the Markov Chain, which is generated e.g. by the Metropolis-Hastings Kernel or improvements thereof. If the new state $x_{i,\text{new}}$ is accepted, the particle is moved to its new location and $x_i = x_{i,\text{new}}$. Counting the number of moves M_i of each particle until it reaches \mathcal{F}_F follows a Poisson distribution with parameter

$$\lambda = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N M_i}{N} \quad (2)$$

for a total number of N particles. Lastly, the probability of failure is linked to λ via $p_f = \exp(-\lambda)$. [11,26]

The independence of the generated Poisson process trajectories must be ensured. This is achieved by introducing seed avoidance [26] and a burn-in period for the Markov Chain, albeit a rather small one [22]. On average, the number of times the LSF is evaluated is

$$N_{\text{tot}} = N(1 - N_b \log(p_f)) \quad (3)$$

with N_b being the burn-in period and the estimator's coefficient of variation results in

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{-\log(p_f)}{N}} \quad (4)$$

2.2 Multi Fidelity Estimators

Multi fidelity estimators are obtained by additive or multiplicative information fusion such that the output of different models is combined in an efficient manner. In the first approach, the output of one model is used and refined by adding evaluations of different fidelity models. [23]

[20] used the control variate framework to additively combine the models and distributed the number of model evaluations optimally with the following formula:

$$E(\mathcal{M}^{\text{MF}}) = E(\mathcal{M}^{\text{hi}}) + \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} \alpha_l \left(E(\mathcal{M}_{l,N_l}^{\text{lo}}) - E(\mathcal{M}_{l,N_{l+1}}^{\text{lo}}) \right) \quad (5)$$

Here, \mathcal{M}^{hi} denotes the output of the high fidelity model, $\mathcal{M}_{l,N_l}^{\text{lo}}$ the output of the l -th low fidelity model for a total of L models with $\mathcal{M}_L = \mathcal{M}^{\text{hi}}$. For the determination of the number of evaluations of each model N_l and the weighting factor α_l the interested reader is referred to [20] or the review of multi fidelity estimators published in [21].

For multiplicative fusion either a Bayesian regression can be performed and a surrogate model is used to link the output of the different models in a (non) linear way [4] or expectation maximization is applied [23]. As the distribution of the moves is Poisson, model dependencies in the moving particles method are taken into account by a multivariate Poisson distribution with parameters $\lambda_l, l = 1, \dots, L$ with L being the number of models. The algorithm is described in the next section.

2.3 Expectation Maximization for multivariate Poisson distributions

First, the structure of the multivariate Poisson distribution and its decomposition into independent univariate Poisson distributions is introduced. Afterwards, the expectation maximization algorithm for multivariate Poisson distributions as a combination of the ideas of [15] and [1] is presented.

Multivariate Poisson Distribution Generally, a random variable $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^k$ following a multivariate Poisson distribution can be described by independent, univariate Poisson variables $Y_m \sim Po(\theta_m)$, $m = 1, \dots, M$ with a link matrix $\Phi \in \mathbb{R}^{k \times M}$ and $M = 2^k - 1$.

$$\mathbf{X} = \Phi \mathbf{Y} \quad (6)$$

The expected value and the variance result in

$$E(\mathbf{X}) = \Phi \boldsymbol{\theta} \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Var}(\mathbf{X}) = \Phi \Sigma \Phi^T \quad (8)$$

with $\Sigma = \text{diag}(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_m)$, because of the independence of Y_m . [16,15]

Expectation Maximization In general, the expectation maximization algorithm finds maximum likelihood estimates of the parameters of probability distributions for a given number of realizations iteratively. It is divided into two main steps starting with the expectation step (E-step), where the expectation of the log-likelihood function is computed depending on the current distribution parameters and realizations. Afterwards, in the maximization step (M-step) the log-likelihood is maximized with respect to the distribution parameters. The algorithm alternates between those steps and terminates after the relative change of the parameters passes a given threshold. [5]

The EM algorithm for multivariate Poisson distributions analogously finds the most likely parameters θ_m of the univariate Poisson distributions Y_m following the above mentioned decomposition for a drawn number of realizations. Afterwards, the parameters of the multivariate distribution are obtained using the link matrix Φ .

Given Z samples of \mathbf{X} , being the multivariate Poisson distribution, a pseudo value s is derived in the E-step which represents the expected value of the log-likelihood of each independent Poisson distribution in the presence of the sample \mathbf{x}_i [15]:

$$s_{im} = E(Y_m | \mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) = \frac{\theta_m P(\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}_i - \boldsymbol{\phi}_m)}{P(\mathbf{X} = \mathbf{x}_i)}. \quad (9)$$

Here, the index $i = 1, \dots, Z$ denotes the sample x_i used and m refers to the independent univariate Poisson distributed random variable Y_m with parameter θ_m at the $(t - 1)$ -th step of the EM algorithm. $P(\cdot)$ are the probabilities of the multivariate Poisson distribution and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_m$ the corresponding column vector of Φ . The probabilities can be computed from a recurrence scheme [14]. Note that the probability of the numerator is readily available when computing the denominator. For the M-step, the ideas of [15] and [1] are combined to compute the expected values of the pseudo values s via

$$E(s_m | \mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) = \sum_{i=1}^Z s_{im} = \sum_{i=1}^Z E(Y_m | \mathbf{x}_i, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}). \quad (10)$$

Finally, the new parameters of the independent Poisson distributions for step t result in

$$\theta_m^t = \frac{1}{Z} E(s_m | \mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}). \quad (11)$$

The E- and M-step are repeated until $\varepsilon < \varepsilon_{th}$ with ε being

$$\sum_{m=1}^M \frac{|\theta_m^t - \theta_m^{t-1}|}{\theta_m^{t-1}}. \quad (12)$$

A suitable value for ε_{th} might be $1 \cdot 10^{-3}$.

2.4 Probability Boxes

P-boxes can be used to describe imprecise probabilities. Instead of using one cumulative distribution function F (CDF) which is known or estimated, an upper

and lower bound on the CDF is introduced, \overline{F} and \underline{F} respectively (see Fig 1). The true CDF is not known. [8,7]

P-boxes are classified as distributional or distribution-free. A distributional p-box has a known distribution family with interval valued parameters. The distribution-free p-box has no restrictions and the bounds are inferred from data. Both can be discretized and treated as random sets afterwards, but the information on the family is lost in the case of distributional p-boxes [2]. Figure 1 shows a distributional or parametric p-box on the left and a distribution-free p-box on the right. For the former, a normal family with interval mean and standard deviation is used ($X \sim \mathcal{N}([-1, 1], [1, 2])$) and for the latter only minimum (min), maximum (max), mean and standard deviation (std) are known, with the tuple (min, max, mean, std) being (-4, 4, 0, 2). Here, \overline{F} is in red and \underline{F} in black. The toolbox by [10] is used to calculate the p-boxes and create figures thereof.

If $d > 1$ for the input domain, the dimensions can be treated as independent or coupled. To couple the dimensions, a copula, also called a dependence structure, is implemented. There are a plethora of different types of copulae. For strictly aleatory uncertainties the copula and the marginal distributions form the joint probability density function (Sklar's Theorem). The copula with standard uniform marginals \mathcal{U} connects the physical domains x_i via $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_d) = (F_1^{-1}(u_1), F_2^{-1}(u_2), \dots, F_d^{-1}(u_d))$ with $u_i \in \mathcal{U}$. [19] To include p-boxes the principle remains the same, but the quantiles u_i lead to random sets $[\underline{F}(u_i), \overline{F}(u_i)]$ [2].

Fig. 1. a distributional p-box of the normal family is seen on the left, a distribution-free p-box with only known minimum, maximum, mean and standard deviation is shown on the right

3 Multi Fidelity Moving Particles Algorithm

As mentioned in Section 2.1 the moving particles algorithm leads to a Poisson process with parameter λ for a single fidelity (SF) problem. Applying the same algorithm to a multi fidelity setting needs adaptations.

3.1 Data structure

At the lowest fidelity the SF algorithm is performed. With regards to the computational costs, the model is usually cheap. The MCMC resulting from the lower fidelity model must be fed to the next higher fidelity model at each move. This is achieved using the scheme by [13], where every generated random number of the Markov Chain is stored. The new particle location is accepted if the LSF value of the current model level is reduced. Since the different models are interdependent, the number of moves of the particles are realisations of a multivariate Poisson distribution.

Another goal is the reduction of particles for the higher fidelity models. As described in Section 2.2, the lowest fidelity model has $N_0 = N$ particles, the higher fidelity models have N_l particles respectively and $N_l \geq N_{l+1}$. This leads to an upper triangular structure of particles if $N_l > N_{l+1}$ (see Fig. 2). The structure is then split into tuple of particles existent for all models. Each tuple forms a category c with category 1 containing N_L particles of every model. The subsequent categories consist of $N_l - N_{l+1}$ particles with less and less columns until the last category C with only lowest fidelity particles is reached. Overall, it must be ensured that enough particles are in each category to maintain independence. The different fidelities can be combined using additive or multiplicative information fusion which is shown in the next sections. Lastly, the algorithm is extended to account for imprecise probabilities.

Fig. 2. The particles of given fidelities lead to an upper triangular particle structure. A category is formed if particles are available for all models.

3.2 Additive Fusion

For additive fusion the multi level version of the moving particles algorithm developed by [22]

$$\begin{aligned} E(M_L) &= E(M_0) + \sum_{l=1}^L E(M_l - M_{l-1}) \\ &= \frac{1}{N_0} \sum_{i=1}^{N_0} M_0^{(i)} + \sum_{l=1}^L \frac{1}{N_l} \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} (M_l^{(i)} - M_{l-1}^{(i)}) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

can be combined with the multi fidelity estimator given by [20]. The resulting estimator reads

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{M}_L &= \frac{1}{N_L} \sum_{i=1}^{N_L} M_L^{(i)} + \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} \alpha_l \left(\frac{1}{N_l} \sum_{i=1}^{N_l} M_l^{(i)} - \frac{1}{N_{l+1}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{l+1}} M_l^{(i)} \right) \\ &= E(M_L) + \sum_{l=1}^{L-1} \alpha_l (E(M_l) - E(M_{l+1})) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

with

$$\alpha_l = \frac{\rho_{L,l} \sigma_L}{\sigma_l} \quad (15)$$

being the weighting factor which is calculated from a few pilot samples. $\rho_{L,l}$ is the Pearson correlation coefficient of model l to high fidelity model L and σ is the standard deviation of the corresponding model. Furthermore, $M_l^{(i)}$ denotes the number of moves of the i -th particle for the l -th model and N_l the total number of particles of the l -th model.

3.3 Multiplicative Fusion

To properly apply the EM algorithm presented in section 2.3 a complete set of samples needs to exist in order to estimate the parameters for the next iteration. Since this constraint cannot be satisfied the parameters are computed in a different way, which was suggested by [1] for the bivariate Poisson distribution and is extended here to a multivariate Poisson distribution. To make the transition more comprehensible, the bivariate version of [1] is stated first and then extended to the general multivariate case. Here, the expected values of the pseudo values s are calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} E(s_m | \mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) &= \sum_{i=1}^{Z_1} E(Y_m | \mathbf{x}_{\text{complete},i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^{Z_2} E(Y_m | x_{2,i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) \\ &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{Z_3} E(Y_m | x_{1,i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

For a total of Z samples in \mathbf{X} , the samples are divided into three categories: complete sample, missing X_1 value or missing X_2 value. The number of samples in each category is denoted with Z_1 , Z_2 and Z_3 respectively.

If applied to a bivariate moving particles algorithm, the last term vanishes, since the adaptations lead to a structure, where the higher fidelity model has less evaluations than the model with lower fidelity. Using this information, the generalized calculation of the expected values for a multivariate problem simplifies to:

$$\begin{aligned}
 E(s_m | \mathbf{X}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) &= \sum_{i=1}^{Z_1} E(Y_m | x_{c=1, l=1, i}, \dots, x_{c=1, l=L, i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) \\
 &\quad + \sum_{i=1}^{Z_2} E(Y_m | x_{c=2, l=1, i}, \dots, x_{c=2, l=L-1, i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1}) \\
 &\quad + \dots + \sum_{i=1}^{Z_C} E(Y_m | x_{c=C, l=1, i}, \boldsymbol{\theta}^{t-1})
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

with c for the category and l for the model. The number of samples in each category is $Z_c = N_l - N_{l+1}$ as explained in section 3.1. The parameters θ_m^t can then be determined from Eq. 11. Since this is the general multivariate case, the interested reader can find the computations necessary for the expected values of the trivariate case in appendix A.

3.4 Extension of the algorithm to p-boxes

P-boxes can be implemented easily using the approach proposed by [2]. Here, the p-boxes are discretized and treated as random sets. In the physical input space these sets form hypercubes, also called focal elements. These can be transformed into the copula space, where they equal points again. For these points, the MCMC for the moving particles algorithm can be performed as usual. It only differs in the acceptance/rejection of the proposal state. Here, a transformation back to the physical space and the solution of an optimization problem is needed to get the upper and lower bounds of the LSF, \bar{g} and \underline{g} respectively. As $\underline{g} > 0$ implies $\bar{g} > 0$, \bar{g} must only be evaluated if $\underline{g} < 0$. At the end, $\underline{\lambda}$ and $\bar{\lambda}$ are obtained which finally result in the upper and lower bounds for the probability of failure \bar{p}_f and \underline{p}_f . If a multi fidelity problem is faced, the implementation of an additive or multiplicative version is needed and the bounds of p_f can be estimated separately.

3.5 Construction of the estimator

The estimator is divided into two parts. It starts with the MFMP which provides the moves of each particle for each fidelity. In Appendix B the resulting MFMP estimator is sketched. At first, a pilot run is done to get the optimal samples and correlations per fidelity according to [20]. Second, the categories are looped,

leading to different \underline{g} , \bar{g} . Then, the moving particles algorithm using the MCMC by [13] is applied. Please note:

- It is possible that a higher fidelity model rejects a candidate that the lowest fidelity model accepts.
- If all particles of the lowest fidelity model reached the failure domain the next higher fidelity performs the MCMC (i.e. becomes the lowest fidelity model).
- If p-boxes are present and $\underline{g} < 0$ for the lowest fidelity (i.e. the previous bullet point is true), then \bar{g} of the lower fidelity(s) is calculated as well.

Afterwards, a post-processing stage is carried out which consists of the concatenation of the categories to form a matrix with the sample structure presented in figure 2 and finally, the additive or multiplicative information fusion as described in the former sections.

4 Examples

This section presents the method by two examples. At first an academic problem is presented, where three independent p-boxes of the normal family are considered for three different LSFs. In section 4.2 a single degree of freedom oscillator [24,25] is investigated. Even though distributional p-boxes are initially stated, they are discretized afterwards. For both examples three models are used, so a trivariate Poisson distribution for the multiplicative information fusion is needed. The relevant expected values for the determination of the parameters λ_l can be found in Appendix A. In order to allow for a comparison of additive and multiplicative information fusion a non-optimal number of model evaluations is used in Eq. 14.

4.1 Academic Example

The LSFs are described by

$$g_{\text{low}}(x_1) = 1 - x_1 \quad (18)$$

$$g_{\text{mid}}(x_1, x_2) = 1.25 - x_1 - 0.5x_2 \quad (19)$$

$$g_{\text{high}}(x_1, x_2, x_3) = 1.3125 - x_1 - 0.5x_2 - 0.25x_3. \quad (20)$$

with $\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ being independent normal families. The p-boxes are given by $x_i \sim \mathcal{N}([-0.1, 0.1], [0.9, 1.1])$. The threshold values in the LSFs are the variances of the sum of normal variables which correspond to the safety index β for non p-box variables resulting in p_f using $p_f = 1 - \Phi(\sqrt{\beta})$ where Φ is the standard normal distribution. The LSFs are depicted in a cut of the (x_1, x_2) -plane in Fig. 3.

The estimator has been run 100 times with a varying number of particles. For the results 500 particles for the low fidelity model have been used. As figures 4 and 5 show, the number of high fidelity particles has been varied between 10

Fig. 3. The LSFs in (x_1, x_2) -plane are shown. The dashed lines represent standard deviations of the three dimensional normal distribution with independent copula

and 100. The mid fidelity model always has 50 particles more than the high fidelity one. The relative error of the lower bound, as well as the upper bound, are comparable to the evaluation of the high fidelity model alone. It is depicted on the left of both figures. The weighted sum (WS) and trivariate EM yield a reduction of the estimator's coefficient of variation (CoV), which is shown on the right of both figures.

Fig. 4. relative error and coefficient of variation of the estimator for the lower bound of p_f

4.2 Single Degree of Freedom Oscillator

The often researched SDOF oscillator (see Fig. 6) is used as a second example. The undamped oscillator is excited by a force $F(t)$ with rectangular profile. If the amplitude of excitation becomes too large, the system fails. The parameters needed are given in table 1. As a dependence structure the copula

$$C = C_{\text{Ind,1D}} C_{\text{Clayton}} C_{\text{Normal}} \quad (21)$$

Fig. 5. relative error and coefficient of variation of the estimator for the upper bound of p_f

Fig. 6. On the left hand side the SDOF oscillator is sketched. On the right hand side the force $F(t)$ with rectangular profile is defined.

Table 1. Definition of the input p-boxes and distributions

Variable	p-box/distribution
r	$\mathcal{N}([0.49, 0.51], 0.05)$
F_1	$\mathcal{N}([-0.2, 0.2], 0.5)$
t_1	$\mathcal{N}([0.95, 1.05], 0.2)$
c_1	$\mathcal{N}(1, 0.1)$
c_2	$\mathcal{N}(0.1, 0.01)$
m	$\mathcal{N}(1, 0.05)$

as a composition of three copulae is introduced. $C_{\text{Ind,1D}}$ is a one dimensional independent copula, C_{Clayton} is a two dimensional Clayton copula with parameter $\alpha_{\text{Clayton}} = 5$ and C_{Normal} is a three dimensional Gaussian copula with correlation matrix

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0.25 \\ 0 & 1 & 0.5 \\ 0.25 & 0.5 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

The problem's LSF reads

$$g_{\text{high}}(r, F_1, t_1, c_1, c_2, m) = 3r - \left| \frac{2F_1}{m\omega_0^2} \sin\left(\frac{\omega_0 t_1}{2}\right) \right| \quad (23)$$

with $\omega_0 = \sqrt{\frac{c_1+c_2}{m}}$ being the eigenfrequency. As lower fidelity models

$$g_{\text{mid}}(r, F_1, t_1) = 3r - \left| \frac{2F_1}{1.1} \sin\left(\frac{\sqrt{1.1}t_1}{2}\right) \right| \quad (24)$$

$$g_{\text{low}}(F_1, t_1) = 3 \cdot 0.5 - \left| \frac{2F_1}{1.1} \sin\left(\frac{\sqrt{1.1}t_1}{2}\right) \right| \quad (25)$$

are proposed. The reduction of input dimension is done using the means of the respective values. For r the midpoint of the interval bounding the mean is used. For the low fidelity model 500 particles, for the mid fidelity model 250 particles and for the high fidelity model a varying number of particles have been implemented and the estimator has been run 100 times. As reference probability of failure bounds

$$[p_f, \bar{p}_f] = [7.662 \cdot 10^{-4}, 1.614 \cdot 10^{-2}]$$

have been selected by running the single fidelity algorithm with the high fidelity model 100 times with 2000 particles.

Fig. 7 shows the estimator's relative error for the lower bound on the left and its coefficient of variation on the right. As can be seen, there is a significant reduction of the relative error of the additive and the multiplicative information fusion compared to the high fidelity model only until at least 90 high fidelity particles are present. Also, for the coefficient of variation a reduction can be achieved. Here, the weighted sum and the EM yield the same CoV as soon as 30 high fidelity particles are available. However, it is seen that a significant reduction of both quantities already is possible if only a few particles can be afforded. In addition, the trivariate EM shows a better reduction than the weighted sum for a small number of particles.

For the upper bound of p_f a reduction in relative error as well as CoV in comparison to the high fidelity model is observed (c.f. figure 8). It holds again that for a small number of particles the EM is superior to WS.

Fig. 7. relative error and coefficient of variation of the estimator for the lower bound of p_f

Fig. 8. relative error and coefficient of variation of the estimator for the upper bound of p_f

5 Conclusions

A new approach using multiplicative information fusion for models with imprecise probabilities has been proposed and was compared to the multi fidelity estimator presented by [20] and the high fidelity model alone. To achieve an estimator using less high fidelity models, an expectation maximization scheme for missing values has been implemented. Even though a reduction of the relative error is only pronounced for a small number of particles for the high fidelity model, it is shown that the proposed method yields an efficient estimator by reducing the CoV.

A non-optimal number of samples has been used in the comparison since the optimal number of evaluations for the additive fusion estimator is only valid for a MCS and not the moving particles method.

The number of univariate Poisson distributions to be estimated scales with $2^l - 1$. More models l lead to more distributions. Therefore, only three models have been used in the examples. Additionally, the smaller p_f the higher the parameters λ_l , which leads to more iterations in the recursive calculation of the multivariate distribution since $\lambda = -\log(p_f)$. As mentioned above, for the bivariate Poisson distribution an analytic solution exists. Comparing it to the recursive calculation for given parameters for the univariate distributions ($\lambda_1 = 7$, $\lambda_2 = 5$, $\lambda_3 = 8$) shows that the larger the sample set gets, the stronger the ratio of the computing time declines, but is still immense (see figure 9). ct_1 equals the time needed by the recursive algorithm and ct_2 the time by the analytic solution.

In conclusion, a successful use of multiplicative information fusion is shown

Fig. 9. Ratio of the recursive algorithm to the analytic solution regarding the computing time.

with a comparable error to additive information fusion. For a small number of particles of the high fidelity model it even is superior. Both versions result in a more accurate estimator than applying the high fidelity model alone, but the computational costs for the multiplicative information fusion are immense compared to the additive fusion, since an expectation maximization instead of a simple addition must be performed. Therefore, further improvements in the EM algorithm like a parallelization scheme are indispensable and should be subject

of further research to decrease the computation time of the recursive algorithm and to be a competition to the additive information fusion.

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A Expected Values for the determination of independent univariate Poisson distributions

Recall that a trivariate Poisson distribution can be written as

$$\mathbf{X} = \Phi \mathbf{Y} \iff \begin{pmatrix} X_1 \\ X_2 \\ X_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} Y_1 \\ Y_2 \\ Y_3 \\ Y_4 \\ Y_5 \\ Y_6 \\ Y_7 \end{pmatrix} \quad (26)$$

If now an incomplete sample is present, the expected values for Y_i result in

$$\begin{aligned} E(Y_1|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= E(Y_1|X_{3,i}) = E(Y_1) = \lambda_1 \\ E(Y_2|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} j \cdot P(Y_2 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\ &\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} \left[j \cdot P(Y_2 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} - j \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_2 = j) BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i} - j, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i})}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})} \end{aligned}$$

with $Po(\cdot)$ and $BPo(\cdot)$ being a univariate and bivariate Poisson distribution, respectively. λ_i is the parameter to describe the independent univariate Poisson distribution Y_i . The remaining parameters are given by:

$$Z_1 = Y_6, Z_2 = Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5, Z_3 = Z_6 = Y_4 + Y_7, Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6.$$

Note, Z is not the number of samples as in Eq. 17, but a random variable. The other expected values are calculated analogously:

$$\begin{aligned} E(Y_2|X_{3,i}) &= E(Y_2) = \lambda_2 \\ E(Y_3|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} j \cdot P(Y_3 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\ &\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} \left[j \cdot P(Y_3 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i} - j)}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_3 = j) BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i}, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i} - j)}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})} \\ &\text{with: } Z_1 = Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6, Z_2 = Y_5, Z_3 = Z_6 = Y_4 + Y_7, Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5 \\ E(Y_3|X_{3,i}) &= E\left(B\left(X_{3,i}, \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}\right)\right) = X_{3,i} \frac{\lambda_3}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7} \end{aligned}$$

Note, here $B(\cdot)$ is equal to a Bernoulli distribution. Furthermore:

$$\begin{aligned} E(Y_4|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} j \cdot P(Y_4 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\ &\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} \left[j \cdot P(Y_4 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_2 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} - j \cap Y_3 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i} - j)}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_4 = j) BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i} - j, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i} - j)}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})} \\ &\text{with: } Z_1 = Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6, Z_2 = Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5, Z_3 = Y_7, Z_6 = Y_3 + Y_4 \\ E(Y_4|X_{3,i}) &= E\left(B\left(X_{3,i}, \frac{\lambda_4}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}\right)\right) = X_{3,i} \frac{\lambda_4}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E(Y_5|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} j \cdot P(Y_5 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\
&\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} \left[j \cdot P(Y_5 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_7 = X_{3,i} - j)}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{3,i}} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_5 = j)BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i} - j, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i} - j)}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{with: } Z_1 = Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6, Z_2 = Y_3, Z_3 = Z_6 = Y_4 + Y_7, Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5$$

$$E(Y_5|X_{3,i}) = E\left(B\left(X_{3,i}, \frac{\lambda_5}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}\right)\right) = X_{3,i} \frac{\lambda_5}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E(Y_6|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} j \cdot P(Y_6 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\
&\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} \left[j \cdot P(Y_6 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} - j \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{X_{2,i}} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_6 = j)BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i} - j, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i})}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{with: } Z_1 = Y_2, Z_2 = Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5, Z_3 = Z_6 = Y_4 + Y_7, Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6$$

$$E(Y_6|X_{3,i}) = E(Y_6) = \lambda_6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
E(Y_7|X_{2,i}, X_{3,i}) &= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} j \cdot P(Y_7 = j | Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \\
&\quad \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i}) \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} \left[j \cdot P(Y_7 = j) \cdot \frac{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 = X_{2,i} - j \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 = X_{3,i} - j)}{P(Y_2 + Y_4 + Y_6 + Y_7 = X_{2,i} \cap Y_3 + Y_4 + Y_5 + Y_7 = X_{3,i})} \right] \\
&= \sum_{j=0}^{\min(X_{2,i}, X_{3,i})} j \cdot \frac{Po(Y_7 = j)BPo(Z_1 + Z_3 = X_{2,i} - j, Z_2 + Z_3 = X_{3,i} - j)}{BPo(Z_4 + Z_6 = X_{2,i}, Z_5 + Z_6 = X_{3,i})}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\text{with: } Z_1 = Z_4 = Y_2 + Y_6, Z_2 = Z_5 = Y_3 + Y_5, Z_3 = Y_4, Z_6 = Y_4 + Y_7$$

$$E(Y_7|X_{3,i}) = E\left(B\left(X_{3,i}, \frac{\lambda_7}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}\right)\right) = X_{3,i} \frac{\lambda_7}{\lambda_3 + \lambda_4 + \lambda_5 + \lambda_7}$$

B Flow chart of the estimator

Fig. 10. Main scheme of the estimator

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